

1 **Revisiting the chronostratigraphy of Late Pleistocene loess-paleosol sequences**
2 **in southwestern Ukraine: OSL dating of Kurortne section**

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4 Viorica Tecsă^{1,2}, Natalia Gerasimenko³, Daniel Veres^{4,1,*}, Ulrich Hambach⁵, Frank Lehmkuhl
5⁶, Philipp Schulte⁶, Alida Timar-Gabor^{1,2}

6
7 ¹Interdisciplinary Research Institute on Bio-Nano-Sciences, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca,
8 Romania

9 ²Faculty of Environmental Sciences and Engineering, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

10 ³Taras Shevshenko National University, Kiev, Ukraine

11 ⁴Romanian Academy, Institute of Speleology, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

12 ⁵BayCEER & Chair of Geomorphology, University of Bayreuth, Germany

13 ⁶Department of Geography, RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany

14

15 * Corresponding author: daniel.veres@ubbcluj.ro

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17 Keywords: loess chronostratigraphy, OSL dating, Last Glacial Cycle, SE Europe, Ukraine

18

19 **Abstract**

20 Due to the general lack of other high-resolution paleoclimate records, loess-paleosol sequences
21 are crucial archives for disentangling past climate variability in southeastern Europe. Here we
22 present results of a multi proxy sedimentological and geochemical investigation of Kurortne
23 loess-paleosol section from southwestern Ukraine, coupled with detailed optically stimulated
24 luminescence (OSL) dating. OSL investigations were carried out on quartz grains of different
25 grain sizes (4-11 µm, 63-90 µm and 90-125µm), using the single aliquot regenerative (SAR)
26 protocol. The OSL dating results are in line with previous findings on dating loess-paleosol
27 sequences along the Black Sea shore in Romania, as well as worldwide: (i) ages obtained on
28 different grain sizes are in agreement for equivalent doses of less than 200 Gy, whereas for
29 higher equivalent doses 4-11 µm ages underestimate the coarser fraction ages; and (ii) an
30 inverse correlation between dated grain size fractions and saturation characteristics is reported.

31 Our combined dating and sedimentological approach would confirm that the
32 investigated uppermost 4.5 m at Kurortne cover the Last Glacial Cycle, adding important data
33 in better constraining local and regional chronostratigraphic correlations. The application of the
34 SAR protocol on 63-90 μm quartz grains on samples collected from the lower part of S1 soil
35 (the Kaydaky unit) and from the Kaydaky/Pryluky units boundary produced ages of 123 ± 10
36 ka and 85 ± 6 ka, respectively. As the temporal range covered by these units in the Ukrainian
37 Quaternary stratigraphic framework is still debatable, our results confirm the broad correlation
38 of the Kaydaky-Pryluky paleosol units at Kurortne with the last interglacial (i.e., MIS 5).
39 Dating the Uday and Bug loess units produced ages corresponding to MIS 4 and MIS 2,
40 respectively, whereas the sample collected from the the Vytachiv unit provided an age of 37.7
41 ± 2.4 ka, assigning this paleosol to MIS 3. On the basis of trends in the magnetic enhancement,
42 the onset of pedogenetic processes likely commenced already around 20 ka, but the formation
43 of the topmost S0 soil has begun after 13.8 ± 1.0 ka.

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45

46 **1. Introduction**

47 Loess-paleosol sequences (LPS) in Europe are important paleoclimate archives for recording the
48 long-term environmental history of terrestrial landscapes for Middle and Upper Pleistocene
49 (Frechen et al., 2003; Marković et al., 2015; Rousseau et al., 2017). The size of the loess fields
50 commencing in the Middle and Lower Danube basins and extending to the Russian Plain (Haase
51 et al., 2007) would roughly equal that of the Chinese Loess Plateau (CPL). This fact and the lack
52 of other long-term paleoclimate records renders the Ukrainian LPS (Fig. 1) as some of the most
53 valuable archives for disentangling Quaternary paleoclimate evolution in the northern Black Sea
54 area (Veklich, 1982, 1993; Sirenko and Turlo, 1986; Velichko, 1990; Gozhik et al., 1995, 2000,
55 2013; Lindner et al., 2004, 2006; Gerasimenko, 2006, 2011; Bolikhovskaya and Molodkov,
56 2006; Matviishina et al., 2010; Boguckyi et al., 2013), and a link between west European
57 (Rousseau et al., 2011; Marković et al., 2015; Sümegei et al., 2019) and Central Asian loess
58 paleoclimate records (Zeeden et al., 2018a; Fitzsimmons, 2017).

59 Albeit significant progress in loess paleoclimatology (see review in Schaetzl et al., 2018),
60 more reliable comparisons between LPS and marine or ice-core records are however needed
61 (Zeeden et al., 2018a,b; Marković et al., 2018; Újvári et al., 2018; Sümegei et al., 2019) for deeper

62 understanding of past climate change and for better assessing the role of loess-paleosol proxies in
63 regional paleoclimate dynamics (Maher et al., 2010; Hao et al., 2012; Constantin et al., 2019;
64 Obrecht et al., 2019).

65 In this respect, local national stratigraphic considerations based on phenomenological
66 appearance of sedimentary and/or pedologic units, and often lacking up-to-date paleoclimatic
67 data and reliable chronological control preclude achieving a uniform approach on comparisons
68 with, for example Marine Isotope Stages (MIS), as proposed for both western European
69 (Rousseau et al., 2017) and the Danube Basin loess records (Marković et al., 2015; 2018). The
70 unified Danube Basin loess framework (Marković et al., 2015) is important for securely
71 correlating different national nomenclatures as it allowed for better integration of long-term
72 trends in loess paleoclimate proxies for both, the Danube loess records, on one hand, and to the
73 CPL loess records, on the other hand (see Zeeden et al., 2018a).

74 For the Last Glacial Cycle (LGC), the Ukrainian Quaternary stratigraphic framework
75 (Veklich, 1993) above the Dnipro unit (dn, previously spelled Dnieper), which presumably
76 includes the Saalian (thus MIS 6) glacial deposits in northern Ukraine but mainly loess and
77 loess-derivates in southern Ukraine, consists of eight main stratigraphic units as following (from
78 bottom): the Kaydaky (kd) soil, Tyasmyn (ts) loess, Pryluky (pl) soil, Uday (ud) loess, Vytachiv
79 (vt) soil, Bug (bg) loess, Dofinivka (df) soil and Prychornomorya (pč) loess. The
80 Prychornomorya unit is subdivided into two loess subunits (the lower 'pc₁' and the upper 'pc₃')
81 separated by subunit (pc₂) which includes incipient soils. The Prychornomorya, Dofinivka, and
82 Bug units are generally considered of MIS 2 age, whereas Vytachiv and Uday units are regarded
83 as correlatives of MIS 3 and MIS 4, respectively. The correlation of units within the lower part
84 of the Ukrainian chronostratigraphic framework is still debated. Some authors correlate the
85 Dnipro, Kaydaky, Tyasmyn and Pryluky units with MIS 8, MIS 7, MIS 6, and MIS 5,
86 respectively (Veklich, 1993; Gozhik et al., 2000, 2014; Boguckyj and Lanczont, 2002; Lindner
87 et al., 2004, 2006; Boguckyj et al., 2013). On the other hand, in several studies the Dnipro unit
88 was correlated with MIS 6, whereas the Kaydaky, Tyasmyn, and Pryluky units were linked to
89 MIS 5e, 5d, and 5c-a, respectively (Rousseau et al., 2001, 2011; Vozgrin, 2001; Gerasimenko,
90 2004, 2006; Buggle et al., 2008, 2009; Matviishina et al., 2010; Bokhorst et al., 2011; Haesearts
91 et al., 2016).

92 In light of such chronostratigraphic issues, better assessed loess chronologies (Újvári et
93 al., 2018; Moine et al., 2017) appear crucial for developing reliable regional stratigraphic models
94 (Marković et al., 2015; Zeeden et al., 2018a), with luminescence dating techniques providing the
95 potential for testing and refining correlations (Stevens et al., 2018; Veres et al., 2018; Perić et al.,
96 2019; Constantin et al., 2019). In order to compare the Ukrainian loess-paleosol
97 chronostratigraphic scheme(s) to the unified stratigraphic model of the south-eastern European
98 loess records (Marković et al., 2015), we focus here on the uppermost 4.5 m of the Kurortne LPS
99 (southwestern Ukraine; Fig. 1) that in our view extends over the LGC. It shall be noted that
100 Gozhik et al. (1995, 2000) investigated the Kurortne LPS in accordance with the stratigraphy of
101 the neighboring section Prymorskoje (as defined by Veklich et al., 1967), and the Kurortne
102 section itself has also been reported as Prymorskoje in some papers (Gozhik et al., 1995;
103 Nawrocki et al., 1999). In these previous works, the uppermost loess unit capped by the
104 Holocene soil was related to the Prychornomorya unit, the underlying two uppermost paleosols
105 were regarded as the Dofinivka pedocomplex, and the underlying thick loess related to the Bug
106 unit. Thus, following these authors, the part of the section studied here (i.e., uppermost 4.5 m)
107 relates mainly to MIS 2. The pedocomplex underlying the Bug unit was consequently regarded
108 as an equivalent of MIS 3. This chronostratigraphic framework was supported by datable
109 radiocarbon dates on bulk organic matter, with the uppermost loess unit dated to 12.6 ± 0.25 ^{14}C
110 (uncalibrated) ka BP, the second paleosol yielded an age of 16.3 ± 0.30 ^{14}C ka BP, and the thick
111 loess below was dated to 21.3 ± 0.30 ^{14}C ka BP and 26.1 ± 0.39 ^{14}C ka BP, respectively (Gozhik et
112 al., 1995, 2000).

113 On the contrary, the detailed study of LPS along a submeridional transect throughout
114 Ukraine (Vozgrin, 2001, 2005; Veklich, 2018) resulted in the conclusion that in loess records
115 adjacent to the Black Sea shore, the Prychornomorya and Bug loess units are mainly very thin,
116 the upper two paleosols by their pedomorphological characteristics most likely belong to the
117 Vytachiv, Pryluky, and Kaydaky units (rather than to the Dofinivka pedocomplex), the latter two
118 often welded and not separated by Tyasmyn loess unit as also seen in other profiles throughout
119 Ukraine (Veklich, 1982; Gerasimenko, 2006; Matviishina et al., 2010). Furthermore, the second
120 thickest loess unit from top to bottom should relate to the Dnipro unit and not to the Bug loess
121 (as suggested by Gozhik et al., 1995, 2000; Boguckij et al., 2013).

122 Such local loess-palaeosol chronostratigraphic issues that apply also to other loess sites in
123 southwestern Ukraine, including for example Roxolany (see contradictory chronostratigraphic
124 implications discussed in Gozhik et al., 1976; Tsatskin et al., 1998; Dodonov et al., 2006;
125 Gendler et al., 2006; Boguckyi et al., 2013; Bakhmutov et al., 2017; Nawrocki et al., 2018)
126 impact upon the regional correlation of records, and the potential integration of Ukrainian loess
127 data into a pan-European loess stratigraphic model (Marković et al., 2015; 2018). This is even
128 more compelling when such records are employed in regional correlations schemes with limited
129 direct chronological control for different records (Necula et al., 2015; Marković et al., 2018).

130 Here we discuss Late Pleistocene environmental dynamics in southwestern Ukraine based
131 on integrating optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating of quartz of different grain sizes
132 (4-11 μm , 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm), with high-resolution rock magnetic data, grain size and
133 geochemical proxies for Kurortne LPS. Through comparison with other records from the Danube
134 – Black Sea loess fields we show that the investigated sequence extends over the LGC, providing
135 an important link to other regional LPS, and a key record for comparison of the Ukrainian
136 Quaternary stratigraphy with the Danube loess model (Marković et al., 2015).

137

138 **2. Study site**

139 The Kurortne LPS (45°54' N, 30°16' E) is located near Kurortne village (Odessa region,
140 Ukraine), at the Black Sea shore (Fig. 1). The section comprises ca. 15 m of intercalated loess
141 and paleosol units (Gozhik et al., 2000), and for this study we have investigated in detail the
142 uppermost 4.5 m (Figs 2-3). In order to augment the existing chronostratigraphic framework for
143 Kurortne LPS, 12 samples for optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating were collected in
144 15-cm long metal tubes from the pre-cleaned sediment wall. For sedimentological and
145 geochemical analyses 145 sediment samples were collected contiguously at 2 cm resolution up to
146 130 cm depth, whereas to the depth of 450 cm sampling was carried out at 4 cm resolution. For
147 ease of establishing a reliable regional comparison to the neighboring Danube loess stratigraphic
148 concept, we follow also the approach of Marković et al. (2015) in defining paleosol and loess
149 units, alongside the Ukrainian Quaternary stratigraphic nomenclature (Veklich, 1993). From top
150 to bottom the investigated sequence at Kurortne comprises the following:

151 The *Holocene (hl) soil* (or S0 following Marković et al., 2015) is a chernozem of the
152 subtype ‘common’, around 1 m thick clearly separated into three genetic horizons (Figs 2-3). The

153 uppermost A1 horizon is dark grey (almost black), silty, carbonate poor, loose and porous, with a
154 granular structure and a gradual transition downwards. The A1B horizon is dark brownish-gray,
155 silty, more compacted than the A1 horizon, and with larger granular structure. Carbonates
156 became abundant from 40 cm depth (diffused carbonate mantle on root channels below 50 cm
157 depth). The lower boundary is gradual. The Ck horizon is pale yellowish-brown loess-like silt,
158 strongly enriched in carbonates (below 65 cm), with very weak prismatic structure, without clay
159 coatings. Small and soft carbonate nodules occur from 75 cm depth, and carbonate nodules form
160 rhyzolithes below 80 cm depth. The horizon preserves many krotovinas and root channels filled
161 with humus, and the matrix of the Ck horizon indicates that it most likely comprises material of
162 the Prychornomorya loess unit (between 0.7-1.0 m depth). Seven luminescence samples (PRI-1.1
163 to 1.7) were collected from the Holocene soil and the transitional horizon Ck to the underlying
164 loess unit (Figs 2-3).

165 The *Bug (bg) loess unit* (1.00-1.35 m) or the L1LL1 (Marković et al., 2015) comprises a
166 thin loess bed made up of light brown-yellowish silt, slightly pedogenetically overprinted,
167 preserving also rhyzolithes and soft carbonate nodules. The lower boundary is well visible and
168 OSL sample PRI-1.8 was collected from the middle part of this unit (Figs 2-3).

169 The *Vytachiv (vt) paleosol unit* (or L1SS1) extends between 1.35-2.00 m and comprises
170 two genetic horizons. The A1k horizon is brown, with weak prismatic structure, slightly
171 compacted, with carbonate rhyzolithes and gradual transition downwards. The BCk horizon is
172 light brown, compacted, with diffused coatings of clay on prismatic pedological structures. It
173 comprises white spots of carbonate and rhyzolithes, and rarely krotovinas filled with loess. By its
174 morphological features, the soil resembles a calcaric cambisol. OSL sample PRI-1.9 was
175 collected from the upper part of Vytachiv unit (Figs 2-3).

176 The *Uday (ud) loess unit* (or L1LL2) (2.0-2.5 m) is light pale-yellowish coarse silt, less
177 compacted compared to the overlying paleosol, structureless, with few krotovinas and rich in
178 carbonates, including soft carbonate nodules at 2.5-2.6 m depth. The lower limit is gradual.
179 Sample PRI-1.10 was collected from the middle of Uday unit.

180 The *Pryluky (pl) paleosol unit* (or S1SS1) (2.50-2.90 m) is a truncated brownish paleosol
181 (the intensity of coloration increases downwards), compacted, with weak crumbly structure and
182 gradual transition downwards. It preserves smaller amounts of carbonates than the Uday loess in
183 the BCk horizon that extends over the depth interval 2.70-2.85 m.

184 The *Kaydaky (kd) paleosol unit* (ie., S1SS2) (2.90-4.1 m) comprises three genetic
185 horizons (Fig. 2). The A1 horizon is brownish-grey, significantly darker than the overlying
186 Pryluky (pl) paleosol, composed of porous coarse silt, with weak structure, with rhyzolithes and
187 desiccation cracks filled with the overlying material. The B-horizon is grayish-brown, porous,
188 loose, with weak crumbly structure, dispersed secondary carbonates and a gradual lower
189 boundary. The B_{Ck} horizon is brown, loose, with weak crumbly structure and “beloglazka” (soft
190 carbonate nodules, up to 10 cm in diameter). The lower boundary is rather irregular, with soil
191 aggregates penetrating down by patches (up to 30 cm in depth) and by cracks (“humus tongues”,
192 up to 50 cm in depth). Sample PRI-1.11 was collected from the transition between the Pryluky
193 and Kaydaky units, whereas PRI-1.12 was sampled from the middle part of Kaydaky B_{Ck}
194 horizon. The morphological and pedological characteristics (ie., the thickness of humified part of
195 the profile, the position of carbonate horizon) of this chernozem soil allows attributing it to the
196 subtype ‘chernozem common’ of the Ukrainian pedological framework (Poznyak, 2010).

197 The *Dnipro (dn) loess unit* (or L2LL1) was sampled only in the depth interval 3.90-4.5
198 m, but it extends up to 6 m depth comprises a light-yellowish silt, porous, loose, with no clear
199 texture and tiny punctuations of manganese hydroxides.

200

201 **3. Methods and instrumentation**

202 **3.1. Sedimentological analyses**

203 As described above, the high-resolution contiguous sampling of the uppermost 4.5 m of the
204 loess-paleosol profile at Kurortne yielded 145 samples for sedimentological and geochemical
205 analyses as shown in Figures 2-3 alongside the lithostratigraphy. The rock magnetic
206 measurement protocol follows Zeeden et al. (2018b) with the dried material filled into 6.4 cm³
207 plastic boxes, compressed, and fixed with cotton wool to prevent movement of particles during
208 analytical measurements at Bayreuth University, Germany. A susceptibility bridge (VFSM;
209 Magnon, Germany) operating at AC-fields of 300 Am⁻¹ at 0.31 kHz and 3 kHz was used for
210 determining the magnetic susceptibility, reported here as mass specific susceptibility χ following
211 density normalization. Maher (2011) suggested that χ lf reflects variability in the concentration
212 and magnetic grain size of loess ferrimagnetic minerals. When pedogenetic processes impact on
213 the primary character of loess, the concentration of pedogenetically formed ultra-fine magnetic
214 particles can be determined by the frequency dependent magnetic susceptibility calculated as

215 $\chi_{fd} = (\chi_{lf} - \chi_{hf}) / \chi_{lf} * 100$ [%] (Fig. 2) and $\chi_{\Delta} = (\chi_{lf} - \chi_{hf})$ [$\text{kg}^3 \text{m}^{-1}$], respectively (see Zeeden et
216 al., 2018b). The χ_{Δ} as function of χ_{lf} (Fig. 4) provides a measure of magnetic enhancement in the
217 course of pedogenesis and has often also been employed in determining the detrital background
218 susceptibility of unweathered parent loess (Forster et al., 1994; Buggle et al., 2014), and it is thus
219 a proxy for inferring the impact of long-term hydroclimate variability on loess-paleosol records
220 (see Zeeden et al., 2018b; Schaetzl et al., 2018).

221 The particle size distribution was measured with a Laser Diffraction Particle Size
222 Analyzer (Beckman Coulter LS 13 320), by calculating the percentage size frequency of 116
223 classes within a size range of 0.04–2000 μm with an error of 2%. Each sample was measured
224 four times in two different concentrations to increase accuracy. The grain size distribution was
225 determined by applying the Mie theory (Fluid RI: 1.33; Sample RI: 1.55; Imaginary RI: 0.1;
226 Özer et al., 2010; ISO 13320-1, 1999; cf. Schulte et al., 2016). In order to better assess variability
227 in grain size distribution, we denote the ΔGSD as the difference of grain-size (GS) frequency
228 calculated with the Fraunhofer approximation (FH) and GS frequency calculated with the
229 Lorenz-Mie theory (Mie) (Schulte and Lehmkuhl, 2018). As the complex refraction index (only
230 considered by Mie) varies for different minerals, within the submicron fractions the ΔGSD proxy
231 indicates the post-depositional enrichment of secondary formed minerals (Schulte and
232 Lehmkuhl, 2018). The variability of low concentrated grain size ranges (e.g. the submicron)
233 within percentage-frequency distributions can be misleading due to the compositional data effect
234 (constant sum of 100%) (Aitchison, 1986; Roberson and Weltje, 2014). Therefore, the vertical
235 variability of bulk sample ΔGSDs is analyzed as centered log-ratio transformed (Aitchison,
236 1986) grain size differences ($\Delta\text{GSD}(\text{clr})$), as these are more robust against other grain size
237 influencing processes especially during sediment accumulation (sheet wash, saltation or
238 enhanced background sedimentation). Data are presented in Figure 3.

239 In order to assess the long-term geochemical variability at Kurortne, the concentration of
240 selected elements was measured on the fine-grained fractions extracted by sieving out material
241 $<63 \mu\text{m}$ and drying it at 105 °C for 12 hours. Eight grams of the sieved material was mixed with
242 2 g Fluxana Cereox, homogenized, and pressed to a pellet with a pressure of 20 tons for 120 s.
243 All samples were measured twice with a SpectroXepos X-ray fluorescence (XRF) device.
244 Subsequently, mean values were calculated from the two measurements following the

245 instructions of Spectro (2007), and variability in selected major oxide data is discussed in Figure
246 2.

247

248 **3.2. Optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating**

249 **3.2.1. Preparation of luminescence samples**

250 The luminescence samples were prepared in the laboratory under low intensity red light
251 conditions at Babeş-Bolyai University luminescence dating laboratory, Cluj-Napoca, Romania.
252 Hydrochloric acid (35% concentration) was applied in order to remove carbonates, followed by a
253 hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, concentration of 30%) treatment for organic matter removal. The
254 coarse grain fractions (63-90 µm and 90-125 µm) were separated through dry sieving. The
255 material was treated with 40% HF for 40 minutes, followed by a 60 minutes bath in 10% HCl
256 and a final dry sieving. For measurement, the coarse quartz grains 63-90 µm and 90-125 µm
257 separates were mounted on stainless steel disks and silicon oil was used as adhesive. The fine
258 fraction (4-11µm) was separated by settling in Attenberg cylinders followed by applying an
259 etching treatment with 35% H₂SiF₆ for 10 days. The 4-11 µm quartz fraction was mounted on
260 aluminium disks from a suspension in acetone (2 mg/ml).

261

262 **3.2.2. Equivalent dose determination**

263 Investigations were carried out on three quartz grain size separates (4-11 µm, 63-90 µm and 90-
264 125 µm) per sample, in order to verify the overall dating accuracy and for obtaining weighted
265 average ages that better reflect the time of sediment deposition. Luminescence measurements
266 were carried out using two Risø TL/OSL-DA-20 readers equipped with classic or automated
267 detection and stimulation heads (DASH) (Lapp et al., 2015), whereas luminescence signals were
268 detected by EMI 9235QA and PDM 9107Q-AP-TTL-03 photomultiplier tubes (Thomsen, 2006).
269 Laboratory irradiations were carried out using the incorporated ⁹⁰Sr-⁹⁰Y radioactive sources,
270 calibrated against gamma irradiated calibration quartz supplied by Risø National Laboratory,
271 Denmark (Hansen et al., 2015). The dose rates used for the coarse (63-90 µm and 90-125 µm)
272 quartz grains deposited on stainless steel disks were 0.130 Gy/s and 0.088Gy/s, respectively. The
273 dose rate for the fine grains mounted on aluminium disks was 0.078 Gy/s at the time of
274 measurement.

275 Luminescence characteristics of fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90 μm and 90-125 μm)
276 quartz grains were analysed using the single-aliquot regenerative dose (SAR) protocol (Murray
277 and Wintle, 2000; 2003). Optical stimulation was carried out with blue light emitting diodes for
278 40 s at 125°C, while the signals were recorded through a 7.5 mm thick Hoya U-340 UV filter.
279 The net CW-OSL signal was evaluated from the first 0.308 s of the decay curve with an early
280 background subtraction assessed from the 1.69-2.30 s interval (Cunningham and Wallinga,
281 2010). Sensitivity changes were corrected using the OSL response to a test dose of 17 Gy
282 throughout the whole set of measurements. A preheat temperature of 220°C for 10 s and a
283 cutheat of 180°C were employed. A high-temperature bleach was performed by stimulation with
284 blue LEDs for 40 s at 280°C at the end of each test dose signal measurement (Murray and
285 Wintle, 2003).

286 The robustness of the SAR protocol was checked by the intrinsic performance tests
287 (recycling and recuperation) (Murray and Wintle, 2003). The purity of the quartz grains
288 extracted was evaluated on all aliquots measured using OSL IR depletion tests (Duller, 2003).
289 Recycling and OSL IR depletion ratios within a maximum deviation of 10% from unity
290 constituted the acceptance criteria along a recuperation signal amounting to less than 2% of the
291 natural signal. In this study none of the investigated aliquots were rejected due to poor recycling,
292 recuperation or IR depletion values.

293

294 **3.2.3. Dosimetry**

295 High-resolution gamma spectrometry was applied for determining the radionuclide activity
296 concentrations. A hyperpure germanium well detector was used for measurements, having a
297 volume of 120 cm^3 , full width at half maximum (FWHM) at 122 keV of 1.40 KeV and a full
298 width at half maximum (FWHM) at 1332 KeV of 2.30 KeV. The dose rates were derived based
299 on the conversion factors reported by Adamiec and Aitken (1998). An alpha efficiency factor of
300 0.04 ± 0.02 was assumed for the 4-11 μm quartz fraction, to account for the lower efficiency of
301 alpha radiation in inducing luminescence (Rees-Jones, 1995). For 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm
302 quartz fractions, the beta attenuation and etching factors were assumed to be 0.94 ± 0.05 and
303 0.92 ± 0.05 , respectively (Mejdahl, 1979). The cosmic ray component of the dose rate was
304 determined according to equations published by Prescott and Hutton (1994). Water content
305 estimation was obtained based on the difference between the raw and the oven-dried weight of

306 material with a relative error of 25%. An internal dose rate of 0.01 ± 0.002 Gy/ka was considered
307 (Vandenberghé et al., 2008). The values for the total dose rates as well as the radionuclide
308 concentrations for these samples are given in Table 1.

309

310 **4. Results and Discussion**

311

312 **4.1. Sedimentological and geochemical data**

313 The magnetic susceptibility (χ) and its field-depended component (χ_{fd}) are reliable indicators for
314 the intensity of pedogenesis and chemical weathering of primary loess (Zeeden et al., 2018b;
315 Schaetzl et al., 2018). The χ record of Kurortne LPS shows high values for paleosols and lower
316 values in loess, varying between $28 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3/\text{kg}$ (the Uday loess) to $94 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3/\text{kg}$ (the Holocene
317 soil) (Fig. 2). The lowermost Dnipro loess unit shows low χ_{lf} values, which strongly increase in
318 the Kaydaky paleosol, especially in the upper part of BCk horizon and throughout the B-horizon
319 (Fig. 2). The Pryluky paleosol shows lower values than the Kaydaky unit with a sharp dip at
320 2.70-2.75 m depth that is also recorded in other proxies (Figs 2-3). The χ_{lf} for Uday loess is low,
321 except a distinctive peak around 210-220 cm depth reflected also in other proxies (Fig. 3). The
322 Vytachiv paleosol shows lower values than in the two older paleosol units. The χ_{lf} values are low
323 in the Bug loess; they start to increase significantly at the depth of 1 m. The χ_{fd} parallels the trend
324 in χ_{lf} (Fig. 2), the two proxies being well correlated ($R^2=0.648$), but showing more variability in
325 the Pryluky, Uday and Vytachiv units. χ_{fd} generally oscillates around 11% in the Kaydaky unit
326 and the Holocene soil, reaching lower minima of 6-7% in the Vytachiv and Bug units (Fig. 2).
327 The magnetic susceptibility threshold at Kurortne can be related with the end of the proper loess
328 formation of the Bug unit. Thus, it is possible to place around 1 m depth the end of the
329 pleniglacial loess formation and the onset of pedogenic processes that lead to the formation of
330 the incipient soils of the Middle Prychornomorya subunit, and subsequently to the formation of
331 the Holocene S0 soil. Figure 4 displays χ_{fd} as function of χ_{lf} from Kurortne compared to data of
332 the Semlac LPS (Romanian Banat), which covers the last 400 kyr and hence almost 4 complete
333 glacial-interglacial cycles. All but one data points from Kurortne mark the same magnetic
334 enhancement path and show an identical detrital background susceptibility as already derived for
335 Semlac (Fig. 4). This points not only to a magnetically homogeneous source area of the dust but

336 also to an astonishing homogeneous magnetic granulometry as indicated by the constant slope of
337 the “true loess line” (Zeeden et al., 2016, 2018b). The homogeneity of magnetic granulometry is
338 in turn caused by similar temporal patterns of long-term hydroclimate variability on LPSs during
339 the Pleistocene and is almost identical across the entire mid-latitude Eurasian loess belt ranging
340 from China in the east to the Danube Basin in the west (Buggle et al., 2014; Forster et al., 1994;
341 Schaetzl et al., 2018).

342 The heatmap discussed in Figure 3a,b demonstrates all measured grain size frequencies of
343 116 classes. It is interesting to note that for the whole data set, the main component of the grain
344 size distribution is in the cSi (ie., 20-63 μm) fraction. Except for thin intervals in the Holocene
345 soil, there are no particles in the mS (200-630 μm), or cS (630-2000 μm) fractions (Fig. 3a). The
346 fC (<2 μm) fraction shows high values in the Kaydaky soil and at the transition from the
347 Vytachiv soil to the Uday loess. The high proportion of the fraction <2 μm may indicate clay
348 production due to increased chemical weathering following pedogenetic overprinting, as would
349 also be indicated by the χ vs. χ_{fd} plot (Fig. 6). The continuous increase in 2-20 μm fraction may
350 indicate the long-term decrease in wind intensity. The >63 μm fraction has the smallest
351 proportion in the Kaydaky soil, and the 20-63 μm fraction shows low values both in the Kaydaky
352 and Vytachiv paleosols.

353 The $\Delta\text{GSD}(\text{clr})$ is used as a reliable indicator of post-depositional chemical weathering in
354 LPS. In Figure 3b the $\Delta\text{GSD}(\text{clr})$ values are shown as a heatmap signature. The values of the
355 $\Delta\text{GSD}(\text{clr})$ signal for the submicron grain size range are low in the lower part of the Holocene
356 soil, the Bug loess, the lower part of the Kaydaky paleosol and the Dnipro loess (Fig. 3b). In the
357 humus and humus-transitional horizons of the Holocene soil and in the depth interval between
358 1.5 m and 3.5 m, the $\Delta\text{GSD}(\text{clr})$ signals for the submicron range increase. The variability in these
359 values partly follows the stratigraphy, increasing mainly in the Holocene soil genetic horizons
360 (A1B) denoting intense chemical weathering. It is noticeable that the high values of the fraction
361 <2 μm within the Kaydaky paleosol are not followed by the $\Delta\text{GSD}(\text{clr})$ signature (Fig. 3a,b).

362 Figure 2 shows the geochemical data denoting concurrent variability in all major oxides
363 between paleosols and the loess units that is well reflected in the lithostratigraphy. The
364 SiO_2 values ranges from 42.7% to 62.7% (average 52.3%). Al_2O_3 is also a major contributor to
365 the sediments at Kurortne, and varies between 7.8% and 12.7%, with an average of 10.4%. Other
366 major oxides are present in smaller concentrations. The Fe_2O_3 content varies from 2.7% to 4.3%

367 (average 3.7%). The K₂O and MgO contributions vary from 1.6% to 2.4% and 1.6% to 2.4%,
368 respectively, both elements have an average of 1.9%. TiO₂ contributes with 0.64–0.86%
369 (average 0.75%), P₂O₅ with 0.13–0.21% (average 0.16%) and MnO is in the range of 0.05–
370 0.11% (average 0.08%). CaO reaches values between 1.2% and 14.9% (average 7.5%) and it
371 reflects well the lithostratigraphic changes between the paleosols and the loess units, attaining
372 highest values in the Dnipro, Uday, and Bug loess units, and lowest values in the Holocene soil.
373 As the trend in other major oxides is inversely correlated with CaO, it indicates that the latter
374 induces slight a dilution effect, which can also be discerned when compared with χ (Fig. 2). An
375 exception is the sharp variability at 2.70-2.75 cm depth which is reflected as a drop/increase in
376 most major oxides (and concordant variability in χ and grain-size; Figs 2-3) except for SiO₂ and
377 K₂O – this would indicate a potential presence of volcanic particles, as tephra layers have often
378 been reported within southeastern European loess records (Constantin et al., 2012; Veres et al.,
379 2013; Anechitei-Deacu et al., 2014; Marković et al., 2015; 2018). However, an alternative
380 interpretation is presented in section 5.2.

381

382 **4.2. Luminescence properties and equivalent doses**

383 The equivalent doses (D_e) were obtained by projecting the sensitivity corrected natural OSL
384 signal onto the dose response curve constructed for each luminescence sample (see Fig. 2 for
385 downwall location of samples). Figure 5 presents the representative SAR growth curves for a
386 single aliquot of fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90 μm and 90-125 μm) grained quartz from
387 samples PRI-1.5 and PRI-1.10. The OSL signals displayed a rapid decay in the case of both fine
388 and coarse quartz aliquots during optical stimulation, the shapes of the OSL decay curves being
389 almost identical to those obtained for the calibration quartz supplied by the Risø National
390 Laboratory (see inset to Fig. 5).

391 Furthermore, the dependency of the equivalent doses on the preheat temperature was
392 investigated for sample PRI-1.7. Aliquots of fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90 μm) quartz were
393 separated into groups of five, each corresponding to a temperature point (ie., 180°C, 200°C,
394 220°C, 240°C, 260°C, 280°C). A 180°C cutheat (test dose preheat) was employed. As shown in
395 Supplementary File Fig. S2, the preheat plateau indicates the thermal stability of the OSL signal
396 and ensures that any thermal transfer is irrelevant. The recycling ratio and recuperation were
397 satisfactory for all measured aliquots.

398 Further on, dose recovery tests (Murray and Wintle, 2003) were conducted to investigate
399 the reliability of the equivalent doses obtained by applying the SAR protocol on fine (4-11 μm)
400 and coarse (63-90 μm) quartz grains from samples PRI-1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8 and PRI-1.10. The test
401 consisted in double bleach for 250 s at room temperature using the blue LEDs with a 10 ka pause
402 inserted between the stimulation. The aliquots were then irradiated with known beta doses
403 chosen to be equal to the estimated equivalent doses, and measured using the SAR protocol. As
404 seen in Supplementary File Fig. S3, very good recovery to given dose ratios were obtained,
405 except for PRI-1.2 (4-11 μm quartz fraction) showing 14% underestimation.

406 Dose response for very high doses was investigated using three aliquots from PRI-1.12
407 (Dnipro loess), and sensitivity corrected growth curves extending up to 5000 Gy were
408 constructed on fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90 and 90-125 μm) quartz grains (Supplementary
409 File Fig. S1). The growth curve was best fitted by a sum of two saturating exponential function
410 such as in the following equation:

411

$$412 \quad I(D) = I_0 + A(1 - \exp(-D/D_{01})) + B(1 - \exp(-D/D_{02}))$$

413

414 where, I is the intensity of the signal for a given dose D , I_0 is the intercept, A and B are
415 the saturation intensities of the two exponential components and D_{01} , D_{02} are the dose levels
416 characteristic of the dose–response curve of each exponential function (Wintle and Murray,
417 2006), parameters which we will refer to as saturation characteristics.

418 From data presented in Supplementary File Fig. S1 it can be observed that the fine quartz
419 fraction (4-11 μm) saturates at significantly higher doses than coarse (63-90 μm and 90-125 μm)
420 fractions. From doses higher than about 100 Gy a significant difference in the response between
421 fine and coarse-grained quartz was observed. Different saturation characteristics of fine and
422 coarse quartz grains have been reported previously in loess samples from southeastern Europe and
423 the Chinese Loess Plateau (CPL) (Timar-Gabor et al., 2012; 2015; 2017). For the 4-11 μm quartz
424 fraction of sample PRI-1.12 we are reporting average values for the saturation characteristics of
425 $D_{01}=170$ Gy and $D_{02}=1355$ Gy, for the 63-90 μm fraction the corresponding values are $D_{01}=41$
426 Gy and $D_{02}= 316$ Gy, whereas in the case of 90-125 μm fraction, saturation characteristics of
427 $D_{01}=44$ Gy and $D_{02}=390$ Gy were determined. Our results are similar with the saturation
428 characteristic doses reported by Timar-Gabor et al. (2017) for worldwide loess and samples of

429 various sedimentary origins (for 4-11 μm fine grains the values for D_{01} and D_{02} were 151 and
430 1411 Gy, respectively; for 63–90 and 90–125 μm coarse grains the values of D_{01} were 44 and 36
431 Gy, respectively, and for D_{02} 452 and 363 Gy, respectively).

432 Equivalent doses were determined on minimum ten aliquots of each grain size separate.
433 Results of equivalent dose measurements and standard SAR performance tests (recycling, IR
434 depletion and recuperation) are presented Supplementary File Table S1. The equivalent doses
435 obtained for the fine fraction (4-11 μm) are higher than the equivalent doses obtained on coarse
436 quartz (except for the oldest sample PRI-1.12), as expected due the contribution of the alpha
437 dose (Table 1, Supplementary File Table S1). We consider the equivalent doses obtained on fine
438 quartz on the two oldest samples (PRI-1.11 and 1.12) as underestimates based on (i) comparison
439 with coarse quartz data, and (ii) widely reported underestimation of equivalent dose beyond 100
440 Gy for loess samples from southeastern Europe and China (Timar-Gabor et al., 2017).

441

442 **4.3. OSL ages and validity of regional correlations based on luminescence data**

443 To establish a reliable chronology for the uppermost 4.5 m sampled at Kurortne, a quartz OSL
444 dating approach was applied using 4-11 μm , 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm grain fractions for every
445 sample analysed. Table 1 presents a summary of the age results, with uncertainties on the
446 individual ages obtained based on the error assessment system by Aitken and Allred (1972) and
447 Aitken (1976). The systematic errors account to maximum 6% for ages derived from coarse
448 grains, and 8% for fine grains, respectively. The systematic error is particularly related to our
449 estimates of the uncertainties associated with the time-averaged water content, beta attenuation,
450 and alpha efficiency factors. The random error represents a measure of the internal consistency
451 of the optical ages and extended to 13% for the coarse quartz grains (Table 1). For the fine grains
452 the random error does not exceed 3%. The weighted average fine and coarse quartz ages were
453 calculated (except for PRI-1.11 and 1.12) following Aitken's (1985) Appendix Band reported in
454 Table 1.

455 For samples PRI-1.12 and 1.11 collected in the BCk horizon of the Kaydaky paleosol and
456 at the Pryluky–Kaydaky soil boundary, coarse (63-90 μm) quartz ages 123 ± 10 ka and of 85 ± 6
457 ka, respectively, were obtained. These ages would confirm the correlation of Kaydaky and
458 Pryluky paleosol units with MIS 5 (Rousseau et al., 2001; Gerasimenko, 2004, 2006; Buggle et
459 al., 2009; Veres et al., 2018) (Fig. 6). The OSL ages obtained for the transition between the

460 Pryluky and Kaydaky units broadly agree with the OSL ages of 70.1 ± 4.0 ka ($D_e = 184 \pm 9$ Gy)
461 and 93.6 ± 5.6 ka ($D_e = 184 \pm 9$ Gy) obtained on 90-125 μm quartz grains, reported by Gozhik et
462 al. (2014) for Pryluky unit in the Maxymivka section, situated in the Dnieper Plain. In the same
463 profile, TL ages of 184 ± 27 ka ($D_e = 475 \pm 47$ Gy) and 169 ± 25 ka ($D_e = 339 \pm 34$ Gy) on 80-
464 100 μm quartz grains were obtained for the Kaydaky unit (Gozhik et al., 2014), that suggested
465 correlation of this unit with MIS 7. Nevertheless, previous studies on the Ukrainian loess-
466 paleosol deposits have reported that TL ages were overestimated (Kusiak, 2007; Łanczont et al.,
467 2013). Moreover, similar studies conducted on Chinese loess have also reported age
468 overestimation for loess samples dated through thermoluminescence methods (Buylaert et al.,
469 2006; Lai et al., 2006).

470 The ages reported for the Pryluky-Kaydaky paleosols at Kurortne are in a very good
471 agreement with results obtained on several loess-paleosol sequences at the Black Sea in
472 Romania, where the first well developed paleosol (ie., S1) underlying the uppermost loss (L1)
473 unit was correlated to MIS 5 (Timar et al., 2010; Timar-Gabor et al., 2011; Constantin et al.,
474 2014). For instance, the coarse (63-90 μm) quartz OSL-ages at Kurortne are in agreement with
475 OSL-ages of 94 ± 11 ka ($D_e = 270 \pm 27$ Gy), 116 ± 11 ka ($D_e = 334 \pm 23$ Gy) and 121 ± 10 ka (D_e
476 $= 342 \pm 18$ Gy), obtained on the same grain size from three samples collected from the S1
477 paleosol at Costinesti loess section (also at Black Sea, SE Romania) correlated with MIS 5
478 (Constantin et al., 2014) (Fig. 6). For samples collected immediately below and above the S1
479 paleosol at Mircea Vodă (Dobrogea, SE Romania), ages of 106 ± 16 ka ($D_e = 310 \pm 10$ Gy) and
480 68 ± 10 ka ($D_e = 221 \pm 5$ Gy) were obtained for 4-11 μm quartz grains, whereas for 63-90 μm
481 quartz grains, ages of 132 ± 18 ka ($D_e = 319 \pm 15$ Gy) and 86 ± 11 ka ($D_e = 237 \pm 6$ Gy) were
482 obtained (Timar et al., 2010; Timar-Gabor et al., 2011). Furthermore, at Mostiștea (Lower
483 Danube Plain, SE Romania), ages of 144 ± 21 ka ($D_e = 391 \pm 28$ Gy) and 97 ± 14 ka ($D_e = 227 \pm$
484 15 Gy) were obtained for 63-90 μm quartz grains on samples bracketing the S1 paleosol
485 (Vasiliniuc et al., 2011).

486 The weighted average age of 61.2 ± 3.9 ka yielded for the Uday loess sample attributes
487 this unit to the lower pleniglacial (MIS 4; Fig. 6) and agrees within errors with the TL-age of
488 65.9 ± 10 ka ($D_e = 128.5 \pm 13.2$ Gy), obtained on 80-100 μm quartz grains reported by Gozhik et
489 al. (2014). Thus it is very likely that the early pleniglacial at Kurortne corresponds to the Uday
490 unit.

491 Sample PRI-1.9, collected from A1k horizon of Vytachiv unit at Kurortne, provided a
492 weighted average age of 37.7 ± 2.4 ka. The available ^{14}C and luminescence data on the Vytachiv
493 paleosol unit in the Middle Dnieper area (Gerasimenko, 2004; Bokhorst et al., 2011; Rousseau et
494 al., 2011; Kadereit and Wagner, 2014) further enable the broad correlation of this unit with MIS
495 3. This is further supported by radiometric data discussed in Gozhik et al. (2014) that suggested
496 the better-resolved Vytachiv unit at the Maxymivka sequence comprises most of MIS 3. The
497 reported OSL ages of 53.8 ± 2.2 ka ($D_e = 111.8 \pm 3.1$ Gy) and 24.9 ± 1.9 ka ($D_e = 55.6 \pm 2.7$ Gy)
498 were obtained on 90-125 μm quartz grains on samples closely bracketing the Vytachiv unit. At
499 Stayky, also located in Middle Dnieper area, Veres et al. (2018) also attributed the truncated
500 Vytachiv paleosol unit to within middle to late MIS 3. For the two samples roughly bracketing
501 the Vytachiv paleosol OSL-ages of 34.6 ± 2.7 ka ($D_e = 101 \pm 5$ Gy) and 26.0 ± 1.9 ka ($D_e = 77.1$
502 ± 2.3 Gy) were obtained for quartz grains of 63-90 μm , and for 4-11 μm quartz grains, the ages
503 of 34.9 ± 3.3 ka ($D_e = 121 \pm 2$ Gy) and 23.9 ± 2.0 ka ($D_e = 81.7 \pm 0.9$ Gy) were reported (Veres
504 et al., 2018).

505 It shall be noted however that in some sequences, the Vytachiv unit consists of three
506 paleosols (Gerasimenko, 2006, 2011; Gozhik et al., 2014). The two distinct peaks in the
507 $\Delta\text{GSD}(\text{clr})$ signal as well trends in major oxides (Figs 2-3) suggest that distinct phases of
508 pedogenesis could be distinguished at Kurortne. In other sections, the middle Vytachiv soils
509 were IRSL-dated to 36.9 ± 3.4 ka (Bokhorst et al., 2011) and ESR-dated to 36 ± 3 ka and 38 ± 4
510 ka, respectively (Chabai and Monigal, 1999).

511 The weighted average age 25.8 ± 1.7 ka for the Bug loess unit allows its correlation with
512 the upper pleniglacial (MIS 2) (Fig. 6). This age is in agreement with OSL ages of 25.8 ± 1.3 ka
513 ($D_e = 56.6 \pm 2.3$ Gy) and 21.1 ± 0.9 ka ($D_e = 43.4 \pm 1.4$ Gy) obtained on 90-125 μm quartz
514 grains from the two samples collected from the bottom and upper part of the Bug unit elsewhere
515 (Gozhik et al., 2014). The dates obtained on the Bug loess at Stayky in the Middle Dnieper area
516 (Rousseau et al., 2011; Veres et al., 2018) also are in agreement with a MIS 2 for this loess unit.

517 For samples taken from the Holocene soil and over the transition to the Bug loess (Figs 2-
518 3), weighted average ages ranging from 0.3 ka to 13.8 ka have been obtained (Fig. 6). The A1
519 and A1B horizons of the Holocene soil yielded ages ranging from 0.3 ka to 9.3 ka, whereas the
520 transitional horizon Ck has been dated between 11.7 ka and 13.8 ka (Fig. 6). The transition from
521 the Pleistocene loess to the Holocene soil was identified on the basis of magnetic susceptibility

522 threshold at around 1 m depth, thus prior to 13.8 ka (Fig. 6). Thus, the OSL ages show that the
523 onset of magnetic susceptibility enhancement at Kurortne precedes the accepted stratigraphic
524 Pleistocene-Holocene boundary dated at 11.7 ka in ice core records (Rasmussen et al., 2014).
525 Similar results have been reported by Constantin et al. (2019) for Roxolany site in Ukraine, as
526 well as in loess-paleosol sites across Romania and Serbia. The slight increase in values of the
527 $\Delta\text{GSD}(\text{clr})$ signal starting from the depth of 1 m in the section supports the assertion on the onset
528 of significant soil formation prior to the Pleistocene-Holocene boundary at 11.7 ka, but likely
529 concordant with the Late Glacial environmental changes (Rasmussen et al., 2014).

530

531 **5.2. Regional correlations based on lithological, pedological and environmental magnetic** 532 **data**

533

534 The correlation of the Ukrainian stratigraphic units Uday loess, Vytachiv paleosol complex and
535 Bug loess to MIS 4, MIS 3 and MIS 2, respectively, was reported in the previous investigations
536 based on pedostratigraphical, palynological and magnetic susceptibility data (Gozhik et al., 2000,
537 2001, 2014; Rousseau et al., 2001, 2011; Gerasimenko, 2004, 2011; Buggle et al., 2008, 2009;
538 Bokhorst et al., 2011; Veres et al., 2018). Two opposite views exist however on the correlation
539 of Pryluky, Tyasmyn, Kaydaky and Dnipro units with MIS stages (see Introduction), as well as
540 on the overall stratigraphy of loess plateau sections in the Black Sea region. According to some
541 authors (Gozhik et al., 1995, 2000; Nawrocki et al., 1999), the uppermost chernozem-type
542 paleosol (ie., equivalent to the paleosol described at 2.90-4.1 m in our record; Figs 2-3, 6) is
543 related to the Dofinivka unit radiocarbon dated at Kurortne (Prymorske) to 16.3 ± 0.3 ^{14}C ka BP,
544 and underlain by a thick Bug loess unit dated to 21-26 ^{14}C ka BP. Thus, this loess unit (ie., below
545 4.1 m in our profile; Fig. 6) is correlated with the earlier part of MIS 2, and the Dofinivka
546 chernozem is regarded as an interstadial paleosol formed after the Last Glacial Maximum. For
547 the other view (Vozgrin, 2001, 2005; Veklich, 2018), based on pedostratigraphical correlations
548 with other LPS along a network of records throughout Ukraine, the uppermost chernozem of the
549 Pleistocene sequences is correlated instead with Kaydaky unit (thus MIS 5), and the loess below
550 with the Dnipro unit.

551 Both our field and analytical data would confirm this second opinion as in the
552 investigated section at Kurortne, the chernozem paleosol identified between 2.90-4.1 m depth

553 (Fig. 6) is a well developed soil, which, judging from its thickness and the depth position of the
554 carbonate horizon, belongs to the same genetic type of chernozems as the modern S0 chernozem
555 (Krupsky and Polupan, 1979). According to previous paleopedological studies (Sirenko and
556 Turlo, 1986), the Kaydaky paleosols in the studied area are represented by chernozems of the
557 subtype 'common'. The soils of the optimal phase of Dofinivka soil formation are chernozems of
558 subtype 'southern', with much stronger carbonatization of their profiles (including the formation
559 of a Ck horizon which is completely saturated by farinaceous forms of carbonates). In other
560 cases, these Dofinivka soils are represented by kastanozems (Sirenko and Turlo, 1986). Both
561 genetic types of aforementioned soils were formed under much drier hydroclimate conditions than
562 experienced during the formation of S0 soil. Paleopedological indices of clay weathering is much
563 lower in the Dofinivka soils than in the Kaydaky soils, and environments during the formation of
564 Dofinivka soils has been interpreted as colder than during the formation of the Kaydaky unit, or
565 the modern climate (Sirenko and Turlo, 1986). Thus, it is compelling to assert that the Dofinivka
566 soils should correspond instead to interstadial(s) event(s), and the well developed chernozem
567 paleosol at Kurortne is not related to the Dofinivka unit but to Kaydaky unit. According to the
568 magnetic susceptibility data (Figs 2, 4, 6), it is the only paleosol which can be compared to the
569 Holocene S0 and, thus, to an interglacial soil. The slightly lower χ values in the Kaydaky unit as
570 compared with the Holocene can be explained by the higher content of young organic matter and
571 likely bacterial induced neof ormation of magnetic particles in the Holocene soil which can lead
572 to enhanced susceptibilities (Maher et al., 2010; Radaković et al., 2019). As recently
573 demonstrated by Radaković et al. (2019) for recent topsoils from a loess plateau in the
574 Carpathian basin, "active" living uppermost soil horizons show the highest magnetic
575 enhancement compared to lower horizons of the Holocene soil and also compared to the
576 Pleistocene paleosols.

577 Furthermore, it has been shown previously (Veklitch, 1982; Sirenko and Turlo, 1986;
578 Vozgrin, 2005; Gerasimenko, 2006, 2011; Matviishina, 2010; Veklitch, 2018) that the Tyasmyn
579 loess unit occurs rarely in the Ukrainian LPS (or it has a very small thickness), thus, the Pryluky
580 and Kaydaky paleosol units are frequently welded without the Tyasmyn loess bed in-between. At
581 Kurortne, the Pryluky unit is partly truncated (only the DCk horizon identifiable; Figs 2-3) but,
582 in general, in this area it is represented by chernozems of subtype 'southern' or by kastanozems
583 (Sirenko and Turlo, 1986). This fits well to the pedological characteristics of the BCk soil

584 horizon, related to the Pryluky unit at Kurortne. The χ values are lower in the Pryluky unit than
585 in the interglacial Kaydaky unit (Figs 2, 6). In other higher resolution sequences, the Pryluky unit
586 consists of three subunits, the middle of which is a thin loess bed 'pl₂' (Rousseau et al., 2001;
587 Gerasimenko, 2004, 2006; Gozhik et al., 2014; Haesaerts et al., 2016). At Kurortne, the sharp
588 drop in both χ and clays within the Pryluky unit might indicate the presence of the 'pl₂' loess
589 material which is indistinguishable visually due to overprinting by post-depositional pedogenic
590 processes.

591 The Uday loess unit likely corresponds to the strong climate cooling of the early
592 pleniglacial as reflected in the sharp decrease in χ (Fig. 2). The increase in clay fraction in the
593 upper part of the Uday loess (Fig. 3) could be compared with the increase in the <0.001 mm
594 fraction in the upper part of corresponding loess unit in other Ukrainian LPS and interpreted as
595 postdepositional reworking from the overlying Vytachiv soil (Veklitch et al., 1967; Sirenko and
596 Turlo, 1986; Gerasimenko, 2006, 2011; Matviishina et al., 2010). On the other hand, an increase
597 in both clays and major oxides (e.g., Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃; Fig. 2) in the Uday loess unit is also
598 described in many sections in Ukraine and Russia. The fact that the Uday loess unit is more
599 clayey and less enriched in coarse silt than Bug or Dniپر loesses lead the aforementioned Ukrainian
600 authors to suggest less energetic wind speed at the beginning of the early pleniglacial.

601 As discussed previously, the upper part of the Vytachiv unit as preserved at Kurortne can
602 be related to the middle Vytachiv paleosol (it shall be noted that in most complete sections of the
603 Vytachiv unit (Bokhorst et al., 2011; Bolikhovskaya and Molodkov, 2006; Gerasimenko, 1999,
604 2010), the middle soil of MIS 3 (Vytachiv) pedocomplex is dated between 36-38 ka BP, whereas
605 the upper Vytachiv paleosol to 28-30 ka BP). The different paleosol horizons forming the
606 Vytachiv unit (likely emplaced during MIS 3 according to loess paleoecological data;
607 Gerasimenko, 2006, 2011; Gozhik et al., 2014) most likely correspond to interstadial events, and
608 in general, they are characterized by low χ values (Rousseau et al., 2001; Buggle et al., 2008,
609 2009). Nevertheless, χ values are somewhat higher in the lower Vytachiv paleosol than in the
610 middle one (Buggle et al., 2008, 2009; Bokhorst et al., 2011), as observed also at Kurortne (Fig.
611 2) and probably characteristic for the South-Eastern Europe including Black Sea region (Obreht
612 et al., 2017).

613 The thickness of the Bug loess at Kurortne strongly differs from its large thicknesses (up
614 to 8-12 m) reported in northern Ukraine (Gerasimenko, 2006; Rousseau et al., 2011; Bokhorst et

615 al., 2011). Nevertheless, already in central Ukraine, the thickness of Bug unit on plateaus
616 diminishes to 0.5-3 m, and in southeastern Ukraine, it does not exceed 1.5 m (Veklitch, 1993;
617 Gerasimenko, 2004, 2011; Buggle et al., 2008, 2009).

618 In the Ukrainian Quaternary stratigraphical framework (Veklitch et al., 1993), the interval
619 before the onset of the Holocene soil at 11.7 ka is related to the Prychornomorya loess unit, and
620 in loess records from south-eastern Ukraine, formation of incipient soils (the middle
621 Prychornomorya subunit) was dated to this time interval (Gerasimenko, 2004, 2011). At
622 Kurortne, χ results allow to place the end of the pleniglacial loess deposition and the onset of
623 pedogenic processes that finally lead to the formation of the Holocene soil already at around
624 13.8 ± 1.0 ka.

625 Furthermore, the identified succession of climatic events at Kurortne can be correlated
626 with other similar loess records covering the LGC in Southeastern Europe, Romania (e.g. Mircea
627 Voda, Costinesti, Koriten and Semlac sections) (Constantin et al., 2014; Necula et al., 2013,
628 2015; Timar-Gabor et al., 2011; Jordanova and Petersen, 1999; Zeeden et al., 2016), and with the
629 astronomically tuned magnetic susceptibility record from the Titel/Stari Slankamen composite
630 record from Serbia on its own age scale (Basarin et al., 2014). Figure 6 shows the correlation of
631 the Kurortne section based on magnetic susceptibility as function of depth to loess sites from the
632 Middle and Lower Danube Basin and to the astronomically tuned magnetic susceptibility record
633 from Titel/Stari Slankamen (Basarin et al., 2014). This correlation is then compared to the
634 benthic oxygen isotope stack (MIS 1 to MIS 6; Lisiecki and Raymo, 2005). All records show
635 similar (climato)stratigraphic characteristics that, however, are temporarily better resolved in the
636 thicker sequences (Mircea Voda, Koriten, Titel). Nevertheless, also the condensed sections with
637 thicknesses of less than 5 meters reveal an interesting pattern of relatively thick paleosol
638 horizons compared to the loess intervals. These paleosol horizons even show typical stratigraphic
639 susceptibility patterns easily recognizable across the Danube loess-paleosol sequences covering
640 the LGC (Marković et al., 2015).

641

642 **6. Conclusions**

643

644 Following a multiproxy sedimentological and chronological investigation we show that for the
645 uppermost 4.5 m of the loess-paleosol sequence exposed at Kurortne, the lowermost loess unit

646 dated here prior to 123 ± 10 ka and corresponding to the Dnipro unit (equivalent to L2LL1;
647 Marković et al., 2015) was succeeded by the formation of a thick interglacial-type chernozem
648 paleosol, OSL dated in its upper part to 85.0 ± 6 ka (the Kaydaky unit, corresponding to S1SS2).
649 Previous research corroborated by our observations indicate that this fossil chernozem belongs to
650 the same subtype ‘common chernozem’ as the modern topsoil, but the carbonates are leached
651 deeper, likely indicating wetter conditions during last interglacial than at present. The higher
652 proportions of $<2 \mu\text{m}$ grain-size fraction in this paleosol also hints at more intense chemical
653 weathering than during the Holocene and, thus, presumably milder climate during the
654 emplacement of Kaydaky paleosol.

655 The Pryluky paleosol (corresponding to S1SS1), overlain by the Uday loess unit which is
656 dated here to 61.2 ± 3.9 ka, is strongly enriched in carbonates, depleted in humus, with lower
657 magnetic susceptibility values and a less abundant $<2 \mu\text{m}$ grain-size fraction than in the Kaydaky
658 paleosol. These data support previously reported observations that the paleosol(s) comprised
659 within the Pryluky unit most likely correspond to interstadial events of the early glacial (with
660 lower chemical weathering indices than the underlying interglacial soil), and the whole
661 Kaydaky-Pryluky sequence is correlative of MIS 5.

662 The Vytachiv paleosol (i.e., L1SS1) is positioned between the Uday loess (L1LL2, dated
663 here to 61.2 ± 3.9 ka and thus corresponding to MIS 4) and the Bug loess (L1LL1, dated here to
664 25.8 ± 1.7 ka, and thus pertaining to the upper pleniglacial MIS 2) both characterized by low
665 magnetic susceptibility values denoting loess accumulation under stadial conditions. The
666 Vytachiv paleosol, OSL dated towards the top to 37.7 ± 2.4 ka is represented by a calcareous
667 cambisol with magnetic susceptibility values and proportions of $<2 \mu\text{m}$ particles slightly higher
668 than in the loess. These facts, as well as morphological features indicate that it represents an
669 interstadial(s) formed during the middle pleniglacial (MIS 3). The observed increase in magnetic
670 susceptibility and in the grain-size fraction $<2 \mu\text{m}$ in the lower part of the Vytachiv unit has also
671 been reported in the other Ukrainian LPS.

672 The Late Pleistocene Prychornomor'ya loess unit dated at Kurortne between 13.8 ± 3.9 ka
673 and 11.7 ± 0.8 ka (the Late Glacial, the last part of MIS 2) is represented by the carbonate
674 horizon of the Holocene soil. The threshold in magnetic susceptibility values at the bottom of
675 this unit marks the transition from the proper pleniglacial loess accumulation to the onset of
676 pedogenic processes roughly around 20 ka. The intense pedogenesis during the Holocene

677 interglacial resulted in the formation of a chernozem soil subtype ‘common’, which is typical S0
678 soil in the studied region of Ukraine.

679 The results discussed here based on integrating luminescence dating with multi-proxy
680 sedimentological data for Kurortne LPS unequivocally ascertain to the last glacial cycle the
681 uppermost 4.5 m of the section comprising the interval between first major paleosol (i.e.,
682 Kaydaky unit) and the Holocene S0 topsoil. This correlation fully supported by the OSL data
683 helps in clarifying local chronostratigraphic correlations, establish more secure reconstructions
684 of Late Pleistocene environmental changes in the northern Black Sea area, and test the
685 correspondence with the Danube loess chronostratigraphic framework as discussed in Marković
686 et al. (2015).

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688

689 **Acknowledgements**

690 This research has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the
691 European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme ERC-2015-STG (grant
692 agreement No [678106]). F. Lehmkuhl and P. Schulte carried grain-size investigations in the
693 context of the CRC 806 "Our way to Europe" funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft
694 (DFG, German Research Foundation) – Projektnummer 57444011 – SFB 806. We thank
695 Szabolcs Kelemen for gamma spectrometry measurements and Dr. Laura del Valle Villalonga
696 for drawing the stratigraphic column.

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1077 **List of figures and tables**

1078

1079 **Figure 1.** Location of the studied Kurortne loess-paleosol sequence in southwestern Ukraine,
1080 alongside the distribution of loess and loess-derivate deposits in southeastern and eastern Europe
1081 after Hasse et al. (2007). Other loess-paleosol sequences discussed in the main text are also
1082 indicated.

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1084 **Figure 2.** The lithostratigraphy of the investigated uppermost 4.5 m at Kurortne loess-paleosol
1085 section, alongside the identified regional chronostratigraphic units of the Ukrainian Quaternary
1086 stratigraphic framework. The sedimentological data include the low-frequency magnetic
1087 susceptibility (χ_{lf}), frequency-dependent magnetic susceptibility (χ_{fd}) and the relative abundance
1088 (in %) of major oxides TiO₂, CaO, SiO₂, Fe₂O₃, Al₂O₃, K₂O, and MgO. Note the reversed
1089 horizontal axis for CaO and MgO. The location of OSL samples discussed in the main text and
1090 Table 1 is also indicated.

1091 **Figure 3.** Heatmap plot of grain-size variability for the 4.5 m investigated at Kurortne: a) the
1092 $\Delta\text{GSD}_{\text{raw}}$ distribution reflecting the difference of grain-size (GS) frequency calculated with the
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1094 (Schulte and Lehmkuhl, 2018); and b) the centered log-ratio transformed (Aitchison, 1986) grain
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1096 fraction $<2 \mu\text{m}$, and the median (μm).

1097 **Figure 4.** Plot of the χ_{lf} (ordinate) versus χ_{Δ} (abscissa) for Kurortne, Ukraine (this study; crosses)
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1099 Zeeden et al. (2016). For location of sites see Figure 1.

1100 **Figure 5.** Representative sensitivity-corrected growth curve constructed for (a), (d) 4-11 μm , (b),
1101 (e) 63-90 μm , and (c), (f) 90-125 μm quartz fractions from samples PRI-1.5 and PRI-1.10,
1102 respectively (See Figs 2-3 for location of samples). The responses to regenerated doses are
1103 shown as open squares. The sensitivity corrected natural signal is depicted as a star, whereas the
1104 arrow indicates the equivalent dose. Recycling and IR depletion points are represented as an
1105 open triangle and an open down triangle, respectively. The inset shows a typical decay curve of

1106 natural CW-OSL signal (open squares) in comparison to a regenerated signal (open circles) and a
1107 calibration quartz signal (open triangles).

1108 **Figure 6.** Litho- and pedostratigraphical columns vs. magnetic susceptibility (χ_{lf}) record and
1109 OSL ages of the Kurortne loess-paleosol sequence (A, B), and its correlations to loess magnetic
1110 susceptibility (χ_{lf}) records of sites from the Middle and Lower Danube basins (C: Costinesti,
1111 Romania (Constantin et al., 2014; Necula et al., 2015); D: Mircea Vodă, Romania (Necula et al.,
1112 2013; Timar-Gabor et al., 2011); E: Koriten, Bulgaria (Jordanova and Petersen, 1999); F:
1113 Semlac, Romania (Zeeden et al., 2016) and to the astronomically tuned magnetic susceptibility
1114 record from the (G) Titel/Stari Slankamen (Serbia) composite record (Basarin et al., 2014) and
1115 the (H) benthic oxygen isotope stack (Lisiecki and Raymo, 2005). The Danube Basin loess
1116 stratigraphic nomenclature follows Marković et al. (2015). The dashed grey lines indicate
1117 stratigraphic correlation levels based on characteristic susceptibility patterns shared between the
1118 records. The OSL ages at Costinesti shown are the weighted average ages of samples CST 11,
1119 CST 12, CST 13 samples (upper part of S1) and weighted average ages of CST 15, CST 16, CST
1120 17 samples (upper part of L2 loess) obtained on 63-90 μm quartz extracts (Constantin et al.,
1121 2014). The OSL ages at Mircea Voda were obtained on 63-90 μm quartz extracts (Timar -Gabor
1122 et al., 2011). The OSL ages at Semlac were obtained on 40-63 μm quartz extracts (upper part of
1123 S1) and 4-11 μm (lower part of S1), respectively (Zeeden et al., 2016). For location of sites
1124 please refer to Figure 1.

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1126 **Table 1.** Summary of the luminescence and dosimetry data for Kurortne samples analysed in this
1127 study. Weighted OSL ages are calculated according to Aitken (1985). The uncertainties
1128 associated with the luminescence and dosimetry data are random; the uncertainties mentioned
1129 with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. All uncertainties represent 1σ . The ages were
1130 determined considering the “as found” water content, with a relative error of 25%; n denotes the
1131 number of accepted aliquots; beta attenuation and etching factor used for 63-90 μm and 90-125
1132 μm fractions are 0.94 ± 0.050 and 0.92 ± 0.050 , respectively; adopted alpha efficiency factor was
1133 0.04 ± 0.02 . The total dose rate consists of the contribution from the alpha, beta and gamma
1134 radiations as well as the contribution from the cosmic radiation. For the down-wall location of OSL
1135 samples see Figures 2-3.

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1137 Figure 1:

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Fig. 5

Table 1. Summary of the luminescence and dosimetry data. Weighted OSL ages are calculated according to **Aitken (1985)**. The uncertainties associated with the luminescence and dosimetry data are random; the uncertainties mentioned with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. All uncertainties represent 1σ . The ages were determined considering the “as found” water content, with a relative error of 25%; n denotes the number of accepted aliquots; beta attenuation and etching factor used for 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm fractions are 0.94 ± 0.050 and 0.92 ± 0.050 , respectively; adopted alpha efficiency factor was 0.04 ± 0.02 . The total dose rate consists of the contribution from the alpha, beta and gamma radiations as well as the contribution from the cosmic radiation.

Sample code	Depth (cm)	Grain size (μm)	Water content (%)	ED (Gy)	U-Ra (Bq/kg)	Th (Bq/kg)	K (Bq/kg)	Total random error (%)	Total Systematic error (%)	Total dose rate (Gy/ka)	Age (ka)	Weighted ages (ka)
PRI 1.1	15	4-11	4.4	3.5 ± 0.1 (n=11)	42.8 ± 1.3	40.6 ± 1.2	508 ± 15	3.2	7.9	4.00 ± 0.06	0.9 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.0
		63-90		1.1 ± 0.1 (n=10)				9.2	5.5	3.36 ± 0.05	0.3 ± 0.0	
		90-125		0.8 ± 0.1 (n=10)				12.6	5.4	3.32 ± 0.05	0.2 ± 0.0	
PRI 1.2	30	4-11	6.2	15.4 ± 0.1 (n=11)	41.3 ± 1.5	39.4 ± 1.5	507 ± 14	1.8	7.9	3.83 ± 0.06	4.0 ± 0.3	4.2 ± 0.3
		63-90		14.7 ± 1.4 (n=10)				9.7	5.6	3.22 ± 0.05	4.6 ± 0.5	
		90-125		13.8 ± 1.1 (n=12)				8.1	5.6	3.18 ± 0.05	4.3 ± 0.4	
PRI 1.3	43	4-11	2.8	24.0 ± 0.7 (n=11)	38.6 ± 0.1	41.6 ± 1.1	485 ± 16	3.3	7.9	3.87 ± 0.06	6.2 ± 0.5	6.1 ± 0.4
		63-90		24.1 ± 2.3 (n=10)				9.7	5.4	3.24 ± 0.05	7.4 ± 0.8	
		90-125		17.2 ± 1.4 (n=12)				8.3	5.4	3.20 ± 0.05	5.4 ± 0.5	
PRI 1.4	53	4-11	2.2	30.4 ± 0.4 (n=10)	37.0 ± 0.9	33.4 ± 0.8	447 ± 13	2.0	7.8	3.52 ± 0.05	8.6 ± 0.7	9.1 ± 0.6
		63-90		28.7 ± 2.0 (n=10)				7.1	5.4	2.96 ± 0.05	9.7 ± 0.9	
		90-125		26.7 ± 1.4 (n=12)				5.5	5.4	2.92 ± 0.05	9.1 ± 0.7	
PRI 1.5	58	4-11	6.7	32.6 ± 0.7 (n=11)	37.3 ± 0.3	35.2 ± 0.3	453 ± 13	2.5	8.0	3.41 ± 0.04	9.6 ± 0.8	9.3 ± 0.6
		63-90		26.6 ± 1.5 (n=11)				5.8	5.6	2.87 ± 0.04	9.3 ± 0.8	
		90-125		26.2 ± 1.0 (n=12)				4.1	5.6	2.83 ± 0.04	9.2 ± 0.6	
PRI 1.6	68	4-11	6.5	39.5 ± 0.4 (n=12)	38.2 ± 1.4	35.5 ± 1.3	496 ± 16	2.1	7.8	3.58 ± 0.07	11.0 ± 0.9	11.7 ± 0.8
		63-90		37.9 ± 1.6 (n=10)				4.6	5.7	3.02 ± 0.06	12.5 ± 0.9	
		90-125		34.8 ± 2.6 (n=12)				7.7	5.6	2.99 ± 0.06	11.7 ± 1.1	
PRI 1.7	85	4-11	8.5	42.9 ± 0.5 (n=10)	36.1 ± 1.0	33.4 ± 1.3	448 ± 12	2.0	8.1	3.25 ± 0.05	13.2 ± 1.1	13.8 ± 1.0
		63-90		41.8 ± 2.6 (n=11)				6.4	5.8	2.74 ± 0.04	15.3 ± 1.3	
		90-125		36.1 ± 2.5 (n=10)				7.1	5.8	2.70 ± 0.04	13.4 ± 1.2	
PRI 1.8	115	4-11	7.7	89.4 ± 1.1 (n=10)	38.0 ± 1.1	39.4 ± 0.5	447 ± 13	1.8	8.3	3.45 ± 0.05	25.9 ± 2.2	25.8 ± 1.7
		63-90		88.7 ± 4.0 (n=10)				4.7	5.7	2.88 ± 0.04	30.8 ± 2.3	
		90-125		62.8 ± 4.1 (n=12)				6.7	5.7	2.85 ± 0.04	22.0 ± 1.9	
PRI 1.9	150	4-11	4.2	123 ± 1 (n=10)	33.1 ± 1.5	36.5 ± 1.0	458 ± 13	1.9	7.8	3.41 ± 0.06	36.2 ± 2.9	37.7 ± 2.4
		63-90		111 ± 5 (n=10)				4.9	5.5	2.87 ± 0.05	38.7 ± 2.8	
		90-125		108 ± 4 (n=12)				3.8	5.5	2.84 ± 0.05	38.0 ± 2.5	

PRI 1.10	227	4-11	1.5	218 ± 1 (n=11)	36.5 ± 0.4	40.0 ± 0.7	458 ± 14	1.5	8.0	3.68 ± 0.05	59.3 ± 4.8	61.2 ± 3.9
		63-90		210 ± 10 (n=14)				5.2	5.4	3.07 ± 0.05	68.5 ± 5.1	
		90-125		177 ± 6 (n=22)				3.8	5.4	3.03 ± 0.05	58.3 ± 3.8	
PRI 1.11	295	4-11	6.7	248 ± 1 (n=11)	32.8 ± 1.3	39.9 ± 1.0	472 ± 15	1.8	8.0	3.41 ± 0.06	72.8 ± 6.0	-
		63-90		243 ± 9 (n=10)				4.2	5.7	2.86 ± 0.05	85.0 ± 6.0	
		90-125		235 ± 13 (n=12)				5.8	5.7	2.83 ± 0.05	83.0 ± 6.7	
PRI 1.12	375	4-11	9.7	283 ± 3 (n=10)	28.7 ± 0.2	33.4 ± 1.5	461 ± 15	2.1	7.9	3.01 ± 0.06	94.2 ± 7.7	-
		63-90		313 ± 15 (n=10)				5.2	6.0	2.55 ± 0.05	123 ± 10	
		90-125		280 ± 11 (n=10)				4.5	6.0	2.52 ± 0.05	111 ± 8	

Supplementary material

Supplementary Table S1. The measured equivalent doses (ED) along with the performance parameters of the SAR protocol for each quartz grain-size of the 12 samples analyzed. The number of aliquots averaged for ED calculations is also given. Quoted errors represent 1σ .

Sample code	Depth (cm)	Grain size (μm)	ED (Gy)	Recycling ratio	Recuperation (%)	IR depletion ratio
PRI 1.1	15	4-11	3.5 ± 0.1 (n=11)	1.03 ± 0.01	0.17 ± 0.06	0.99 ± 0.01
		63-90	1.1 ± 0.1 (n=10)	1.03 ± 0.01	0.45 ± 0.27	1.00 ± 0.01
		90-125	0.8 ± 0.1 (n=10)	1.02 ± 0.01	1.06 ± 0.34	0.99 ± 0.01
PRI 1.2	30	4-11	15.4 ± 0.1 (n=11)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01
		63-90	14.7 ± 1.4 (n=10)	1.04 ± 0.01	0.06 ± 0.02	1.00 ± 0.01
		90-125	13.8 ± 1.1 (n=12)	1.03 ± 0.01	0.18 ± 0.05	0.98 ± 0.01
PRI 1.3	43	4-11	24.0 ± 0.7 (n=11)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01
		63-90	24.1 ± 2.3 (n=10)	1.04 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.01	1.00 ± 0.01
		90-125	17.2 ± 1.4 (n=12)	1.03 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.03	0.98 ± 0.01
PRI 1.4	53	4-11	30.4 ± 0.4 (n=10)	1.00 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01
		63-90	28.7 ± 2.0 (n=10)	1.04 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01
		90-125	26.7 ± 1.4 (n=12)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.06 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01
PRI 1.5	58	4-11	32.6 ± 0.7 (n=11)	1.01 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01
		63-90	26.6 ± 1.5 (n=11)	1.03 ± 0.01	0.05 ± 0.01	1.00 ± 0.01
		90-125	26.2 ± 1.0 (n=12)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.06 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01
PRI 1.6	68	4-11	39.5 ± 0.4 (n=12)	1.01 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01
		63-90	37.9 ± 1.6 (n=10)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.02	1.00 ± 0.01
		90-125	34.8 ± 2.6 (n=12)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01
PRI 1.7	85	4-11	42.9 ± 0.5 (n=10)	1.00 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.01
		63-90	41.8 ± 2.6 (n=11)	1.01 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01
		90-125	36.1 ± 2.5 (n=10)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.03	0.98 ± 0.01
PRI 1.8	115	4-11	89.4 ± 1.1 (n=10)	0.97 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.01
		63-90	88.7 ± 4.0 (n=10)	1.00 ± 0.01	0.06 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.01
		90-125	62.8 ± 4.1 (n=12)	1.00 ± 0.01	0.14 ± 0.04	0.96 ± 0.01
PRI 1.9	150	4-11	123 ± 1 (n=10)	0.97 ± 0.01	0.02 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.01
		63-90	111 ± 5 (n=10)	1.00 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.01	1.00 ± 0.01
		90-125	108 ± 4 (n=12)	0.98 ± 0.01	0.05 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.01
PRI 1.10	227	4-11	218 ± 1 (n=11)	0.93 ± 0.01	0.05 ± 0.01	0.93 ± 0.01
		63-90	210 ± 10 (n=14)	0.96 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.01
		90-125	177 ± 6 (n=22)	0.96 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.01
PRI 1.11	295	4-11	248 ± 1 (n=11)	0.94 ± 0.01	0.06 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.01
		63-90	243 ± 9 (n=10)	0.94 ± 0.01	0.06 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.01
		90-125	235 ± 13 (n=12)	0.94 ± 0.01	0.11 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.01
PRI 1.12	375	4-11	283 ± 3 (n=10)	0.93 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.01
		63-90	313 ± 15 (n=10)	0.95 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.03	0.96 ± 0.01
		90-125	280 ± 11 (n=10)	0.93 ± 0.01	0.13 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.01

Supplementary Figure S1. Comparison between extended dose-response curves constructed for sample PRI 1.12 using fine 4-11 μm quartz grains, coarse 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm quartz grains. The growth patterns were best described by a sum of two saturating exponential functions. A test dose of 17 Gy was used throughout the measurements. Data presented is the average obtained on 3 aliquots.

Supplementary Figure S2. Equivalent dose dependence on preheat temperatures for fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90 μm) quartz fractions from sample PRI 1.7. A 180°C cutheat (test dose preheat) was employed.

Supplementary Figure S3. Dose recovery test results for fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90 μm) quartz fractions from samples PRI 1.2, PRI 1.4, PRI 1.6, PRI 1.8 and PRI.10. The given irradiation doses were chosen to match the equivalent dose of each sample. The solid line indicates the ideal 1:1 dose recovery ratio while the dash lines bracket a 10% variation from unity.